

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

4th TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Multi-objective power management of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in grid services applications
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	MMHESS
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Energy Lab 2.0, Karlsruhe Institute of technology (KIT)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Hybrid energy storage systems; power management; grid interface; battery aging
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	18/05/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	31/05/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	21/05/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	29/05/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	6
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	2 Holidays in Germany (20 May and 30 May) and 2 weekends
Number of days using the RI	7
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
The scope of this research was to prove the effectiveness of the implemented PMS in the management of the power shares among the generation, energy storage devices and the grid by means of accurate models already developed by the KIT Energy Lab 2.0 or hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testings available at KIT Energy Lab 2.0. This can be also used not only to assess the	

reduction of the power fluctuations at the point of common coupling (PCC), but also to evaluate the cycle aging of the hybrid energy storage devices, with a particular focus on the Li-ion battery cycle aging due to the imposed operating conditions. Specifically, main batteries operation modes typical of grid services (e.g. frequency control, load peak shifting or levelling, etc) will be investigated determining the advantages at grid level. The obtained results, in terms of battery power and SoC trends will be applied at the e-StorHy Lab of University of Perugia to perform related accelerated aging tests to validate benefits of the PMS and HESS implementation also in terms of battery lifespan extension.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The tests were carried out at the RI provider on the installed Power hardware In the Loop (PHIL) test facility. Specifically, the Simulink model I implemented was integrated in the RI software (OpalRT) to test cases of interest, defined together with the RI provider. By means of PHIL, I have been able to verify the effectiveness of the implemented multi-objective stochastic algorithm in managing a battery-flywheel hybrid energy storage system. In detail, the battery was simulated while the real flywheels installed at Energy Lab 2.0 were used. This to prove the reliability of the implemented power management strategy and to obtain useful results to perform the subsequent battery aging tests at e-StorHy lab of the University of Perugia.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

The initial outcomes of the work demonstrate the extension of the battery lifespan by means of accelerated aging on Li-ion batteries by testing the multi-objective power management strategy in a real PHIL facility, including real flywheel energy storage systems. The results will be used for the subsequent aging tests at our e-StorHy Lab of the University of Perugia. The procedure for the assessment of battery lifespan extension in case of HESS with respect to not-hybrid ESS (only battery) will follow the implemented one presented in (L. Barelli et al, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2019.02.143). The produced dataset (three phase voltage, current, harmonic distortion, active and reactive power measurements, etc.) at the Energy Lab 2.0 will be used to define specific operating patterns for assessing Li-ion aging under different operating conditions and comparing lifespan extension in case of flywheel hybridization with respect to a not-hybridized Li-ion battery energy storage system. This to demonstrate the benefits introduced by hybridization and the developed power management.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The obtained results, related to the PHIL simulations of the developed model including real flywheels at Energy Lab 2.0, will be used to validate and to make a more accurate modelling of the flywheel for the subsequent accelerated aging tests. This to be as close as possible to the real system, in order to prove the benefits introduced by the hybridization of complementary storage technologies such as batteries and flywheels. Specifically, the losses and features of the real flywheel system installed at Energy Lab 2.0 at different state of charges will be implemented in the developed model. Then, the model will be updated and simulations' outcomes will be processed to design an experimental battery aging comparing hybrid storage with the case of only battery storage system, to assess the lifespan extension of the battery obtained by means of flywheel operation and stochastic power management.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)					
PHIL simulations were carried out on specific cases of interest selected with the RI provider to test the model including real flywheels. The produced dataset (three phase voltage, current, harmonic distortion, active and reactive power measurements, etc.) will be used to define specific operating patterns for assessing Li-ion battery aging under different operating conditions and comparing lifespan extension in case of flywheel hybridization with respect to a not-hybridized Li-ion battery energy storage system.					
Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)					
No problems were encountered during the TNA Access at the Energy Lab 2.0.					
Intended publications					
The outcomes of the activity realized both in the TNA-Access ambit and at the e-StorHy Lab of the University of Perugia will be object of joint publications in International Journals and/or Conferences. The European Union support and StoRIES project will be acknowledged.					
Data management					
Conclusions / additional comments					
Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <i>receipt of EC user questionnaire: e7ad470c-9861-4756-ac22-82563aaf651c</i>					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

